

Integrating and processing building energy data to support decision making

Leandro Madrazo, Álvaro Sicilia, Marco Massetti, Fabian López Plazas, Eric Ortet
ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle
Ramon Llull University
Barcelona, Spain
madrazo@salleurl.edu

Abstract—The vast amount of data from multiple domains and sources available today is a valuable resource for improving energy use in buildings. We have created ENERSI, a platform which enables the development of services to integrate and analyse data from multiple sources, including: Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), cadastre, geographical data, census sections, technical building inspections, catalogues of refurbishment measures, and building renovation assessment tools. In this paper, we present two platform services based on the integration of these data which are addressed to two specific end-users: one that enables building owners to know the performance of their dwelling, and suggests recommendations to improve it; and a second one, for city planners to assess the performance of a district, municipality or region, in order to identify urban areas and groups of buildings to be improved, and the corresponding investment costs. The purpose of these services is to provide each type of user with a comprehensive and synthetic view of the energy performance, at the building and urban levels, which enables them to assess their current status in terms of energy efficiency and take decisions to improve it. This paper introduces the two services that will be publicly available in the ENERSI web portal and in the websites of the public administrations which have provided support to the project. The experience of developing these services has shown that the exploitation of integrated data is only possible if the needs of specific end-users have been properly identified, so that the information is presented to them in ways that they can easily understand in order to take decisions to improve building energy efficiency in their particular decision-making realm.

Keywords—Energy Performance Certificates; energy data; energy information system

I. ENERGY INFORMATION PLATFORMS

In recent years, a variety of platforms have been developed to take advantage of this increased availability of energy related

data. Some of these systems rely on the static data of the building stock. Sunroof, for example, uses the vast amount of geo-referenced data from Google to evaluate the potential of photovoltaic production on roofs¹. Other systems collect data from energy experts, in order to create a collective knowledge base which helps to take better informed decisions. For instance, E2KnowHow gathers data facilitated by architects and consultants and process them with a software that learns from the experience of the users². Other platforms, such as Construction21, provide a social network for the different agents in the construction sector to exchange information and experiences³. The areas covered by these information systems data span from buildings to districts, from cities to regions and even countries. For instance, the EU Building Stock Observatory, provides a “comprehensive tool monitors policy implementation in the European Member States and presents country specific data.”⁴

More and more data is available in an open format, for instance, the CENED – Certificazione ENergetica degli EDifici, in Italy, has published the Energy Performance Certificates of the Lombardia region as open data⁵, and the Department for Communities and Local Government in the UK has published the Energy Performance of Buildings Data of England and Wales in the same format⁶. Energy information systems have been developed to make these data accessible to a variety of users⁷. However, most of these systems only display data, rather than integrating data from multiple sources to derive qualified information from their analysis. The Energy Label Atlas⁸, for instance, displays the energy labels of all buildings in The Netherlands in a user-friendly interface. Some other systems aimed at visualizing data from various sources, in order to make their potential relationships understandable to end-users. For example, SUNSHINE integrates geometrical data of buildings with their thermo-physical properties and climate data.

¹ <https://www.google.com/get/sunroof>

² <http://e2knowhow.com>

³ <http://www.construction21.org>

⁴ <http://bpie.eu/focus-areas/buildings-data-and-tools/>

⁵ <http://www.dati.gov.it/dataset/cened-certificazione-energetica-degli-edifici>

⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/energy-performance-of-buildings-certificates>

⁷ <http://www.energysavingtrust.org.uk>

⁸ <http://energielabelatlas.nl>

Moreover, it provides a 3d interface to visualize the energy performance of buildings [1].

The limited analytical capabilities of existing energy information systems are due to the segregation of the available data. Often, information is stored in dedicated databases, which do not provide the information that is needed to gain a comprehensive understanding of a complex problem such as building energy performance, which involves multiple domains and experts. For example, in Catalonia, the EPC data and the technical inspection of buildings, which refer to the same building stock, have been collected in separated repositories by two different public institutions: EPCs are managed by the Catalan Institute for Energy (Insitut Català d'Energia, ICAEN) and the technical inspections by the Housing Agency (Agència de l'Habitatge de Catalunya, AHC). Today, ICAEN makes use of EPC data by providing web-based services such as a simulator of retrofit measures for building owners [2], and a web-based application to search and display energy certificates. However, these energy information databases are limited to the visualization of a single data source (e.g. EPCs or building technical inspections).

There is a need for platforms that provide services to integrate multiple data sources, and most importantly, which provide advanced tools to analyse and visualise the integrated data so that users in various domains (e.g. private owners, architects, planners, policy makers, consultants, builders) can access the information they need to take better informed decisions in their respective decision making realms. For instance, an integration of the two data sources, from ICAEN and AHC, would facilitate the identification of buildings which the technical inspection recommended to renovate with an EPC below the efficiency standards, so that owners and technicians can consider measures to improve the energy efficiency as they undertake the renovation of the building. Moreover, the value of EPC data could be further enhanced by combining them with other data such as the building stock, geographical location, cadastral data, refurbishment intervention savings, building regulations, etc. This paves the way for a new range of analysis that can help to reduce the energy use of buildings.

In the next sections we describe some of the services developed with the ENERSI platform tools to integrate data provided by the two public institutions, ICAEN and AHC, along with other data sources, with the purpose to facilitate to specific end-users –building owners and planners– the assessment of the energy performance of buildings and building areas and facilitate the adoption of measures to improve their energy efficiency.

II. ENERSI: INTEGRATION, ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION OF ENERGY INFORMATION

The aim of the ENERSI project is to develop a platform that enables specific users to integrate and to analyse energy related data in their specific decision making realms in order to get a better understanding of the issues at stake with regard to improving building energy performance. The ENERSI platform is an energy information system that provides advanced energy services to different agents based on the integration of data from multiple domains and formats. It has been developed to overcome the data segregation by providing services to integrate

data from multiple sources and domains using Semantic Web technologies.

The platform enables the development of ad hoc advanced services which suit to the available data and to the objectives of specific users. Specifically, it provides services for three realms: architecture – e.g. analysing buildings' performance to improve their energy efficiency –, distribution – improving the deployment of smart grids –, and exploitation – integrating energy related data for citizens and companies to make use of them. The services that ENERSI provides can be tailored to the particular needs of users in these three realms. The data that users provide is enriched with the data already contained in the platform. This enriched data is then analysed and processed to suit the needs of specific users. In this paper, we describe two of the applications which we have developed in the architecture realm.

The ultimate objective of the platform is to help to build knowledge from information. This involves the integration of data from multiple realms, to analyse the data according to the needs of the users, and to present the analysed information in a meaningful and understandable manner.

A. Data integration and analysis

Energy performance is a fuzzy and generic concept. Therefore, it is necessary to formulate it in a transparent and unambiguous way, specifying what has to be known and measured, and how. For these purposes, it is fundamental to define proper indicators that can be calculated from the available data from the various domains and sources; indicators which need to be tailored to the knowledge and needs of the end-users of the platform services.

The integration of energy related data from different sources makes it possible to obtain indicators which can fulfil the needs of different agents involved in the improvement of buildings' energy efficiency: owners of dwellings and buildings, urban planners and architects, energy consultants and refurbishment specialists, building components manufacturers and contractors, among other. Furthermore, the indicators that can be calculated from multiple data sources need to take into account the differences in scale (state, region, municipality, district, building), the update and maintenance of the data available, and the information they provide (final energy, primary energy, CO₂ emissions, etc.)

The main data source used to obtain the ENERSI indicators are the EPCs, from which data about building energy performance are obtained (final energy consumption, primary energy consumption, CO₂ emissions). Besides, EPCs contain information about the physical characteristics of the buildings (construction year, typology, envelope, transmittances) and the building energy equipment (heating, cooling, and lighting).

These data obtained from EPCs are combined with data from other sources such as cadastral information, technical inspections of buildings and simulators of refurbishment measures [2], among other. The integration of these data enables us to obtain indicators that ENERSI offers to specific users to evaluate the performance of buildings and take measures to improve it.

The design of the services of the platform depends on their final purpose: benchmarking, ranking, energy diagnosis of specific area, defining retrofit strategies, etc. The indicators must be also aligned with the needs of the users of these services. For example, a public administration might be interested in the aggregated values for the whole territory under its jurisdiction, such as total CO₂ emissions of the municipality. However, this indicator might not be relevant for a building owner who is only interested in the energy consumption of his or her building.

To define the performance indicators we have adhered to national and international standards on EPC such as ISO13790:2008 [3] and to definitions provided by the Datamine project [4], and the Directive on the energy performance of buildings [5] which have been transposed to the Spanish regulation [6]. The main indicators on which ENERSI works are:

- **Urban scale:** size of municipality, census unit, number of buildings, age of buildings, type of construction, type of use.
- **Building characteristics:** thermal transmittance of building elements (walls, roofs, windows.). Performance of energy systems (COP, EER).
- **Energy consumption:** total energy consumption by building, consumption by energy service, consumption by energy source.
- **Energy efficiency:** total primary energy consumption and energy service, total CO₂ emissions and energy service
- **Costs:** annual energy cost by building, energy costs by used source, energy costs by municipality, by census unit, etc.

The data integration enables the creation of additional indicators as the amount and sources of data available increases. Some examples of indicators which could be calculated if the data were available are:

- **Socioeconomic:** from data on disposable income, unemployment rates, access to housing.
- **Health:** based on data on health costs, comfort and health conditions in homes.
- **Mobility:** based on data on energy consumption and emissions associated with transport, travel costs, etc.

Fig. 1. Renew your building: Step 1

These indicators would enable the analysis and planning of actions in other areas of interest, such as energy poverty, and mitigation of environmental impact, among others.

B. ENERSI: a platform to develop energy information services

Building energy performance depends on the decisions of very different actors operating in their respective domains, from the public administration that defines the policies and budgets to orient the construction sector to the building occupant that uses the building. Each actor requires appropriate and understandable information in order to take well-informed decisions that help to save energy. To demonstrate the functionalities of the ENERSI platform for specific users, we have developed energy information services focused on the analysis of the 400,000 EPCs records facilitated by the Catalan Institute for Energy (ICAEN). Using the ENERSI platform's tools, these EPC data has been integrated with 8,000 records from the Spanish gazetteer provided by the Geographical Information National Institute (CNIG), data from Spanish cadastral agency, data from the National Strategy for the Energy Refurbishment of the building stock, and census sections data from National Institute of Statistics (INE).

The services developed integrate these diverse data sources in order to facilitate the adoption of actions to retrofit the building stock, by private owners and by public authorities. For this purpose, we have taken as a reference the guidelines of the National Strategy for the Energy Refurbishment, whose purpose is to undertake deep renovations to achieve significant reductions in the building energy consumption. [7]

III. USER ORIENTED SERVICES

Two services have been developed based on the integration of ECP data with other data sources, each one oriented to a different kind of users: 1. "Renew your building", aimed at private building owners, and 2. "Renew your city", focusing on urban planning agencies in the public administration. Both services have been implemented as easy-to-use web-based applications which guide the user in a step-by-step fashion. In order to identify the needs of the end-users, a series of interviews and meetings have been conducted with representatives of the two public institutions which have provided their data, ICAEN and ACH. They have also made suggestions about the type of information a citizen would need to understand the benefits of undertaking a renovation in their dwelling or building, based on the information provided by the services.

1. ENERVAL: Renew your building

This on-line application named ENERVAL has been designed to inform owners about the energy performance of their building or dwelling, to compare it with similar buildings, to identify energy saving measures and their costs. The interaction is based on a sequence of five steps.

Step 1 - The user identifies the building indicating the address (Fig. 1).

Step 2 - The building is displayed in a map, together with other information such as use, year of construction, energy consumption, CO₂ emissions and certification rating and status of the technical building inspection (Fig. 2). To help users, each

term is accompanied by an explanation that appears as required when the user moves the cursor on it. Only the performance indicators which are relevant to the owner are shown to avoid an excess of information: CO₂ emissions, which indicate the impact of building use on climate change, and non-renewable primary energy, to show the consumption of energy resources.

The standard visualization of energy rating used in the EU, which is easy to recognize for non-expert users, is shown. In the graphic, the building rating is compared with reference values of a building that complies with current Spanish energy certification requirements. The rating is explained to the user in simple terms, so that they can understand the impact that a certain label has in energy consumption and building performance.

The application alerts users if the building does not meet with the energy certification requirements and informs them of the obligation of the technical inspections). Also, the user is alerted if the building performance is significantly lower than the average for the buildings of the same category.

Step 3 – Energy saving measures for the building are proposed to the user. The suggestions take into account the characteristics of the building, climate conditions and the type of energy systems used (Fig. 3).

ENERSI derives the type of construction of the building (for instance: light wall, single massive wall, or cavity wall; pitched roof or flat roof; etc.) from the period of construction, building use and the number of flats. Furthermore, it proposes measures to improve the building components and mechanical systems. For each measure the expected energy and economic savings, investment and maintenance costs, and time required for the investment return are indicated. These results are obtained from the ICAEN simulator and the National Strategy for the Energy Refurbishment.

Fig. 3. Renew your building: Step 3

Fig. 4. Renew your building: Step4

Step 4 – Financial programs are suggested to seek funding to carry out the renovation (Fig. 4).

Step 5 – Finally, the user downloads a report of the analysis in .pdf format.

2. ENERPLAN: Renew your city

The users of this on-line application called ENERPLAN are typically experts working for the administration (urban planners, policy makers, politicians) who need to know how the building stock is performing – in terms of energy consumption and carbon emissions – in certain urban areas, the areas in which is more adequate to carry out refurbishment projects, and how these projects can be implemented with the available budget. The application guides the user along five steps.

Step 1 – The expert finds the area of interest, typically a city, town or district. A bar chart summarizing the EPC of the buildings of the area is displayed for each area at a certain scale (province, county or city). When an area is selected, its indicators are compared with those of the area at a higher scale. For example, when a city is selected its EPC chart label is compared with the EPC chart of the county to which the city belongs. If a city is selected, the census sections are displayed in a map which shows the most common energy labels in that area. The user can visually compare this urban area with nearby areas

Fig. 2. Renew your building: Step 2

with regard to the number of the buildings, the energy consumption values and the CO₂ emissions (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Renew your city: Step1 Browsing Counties, cities, and censal sections

Fig. 6. Renew your city: Step 2 (primary energy use)

Step 2 – ENERSI summarizes the building performance in the area in bar charts (Primary Energy or CO₂ emissions indicators). The buildings are clustered according to the National Strategy for the Energy Refurbishment by year of construction, number of floors and residential type (single or multi-family). The user can focus on one type of building to know the investment needed to carry out retrofitting measures and the energy savings achieved after the renovation of all those buildings in the area. Then, the user can set up different scenarios of energy saving by choosing the cluster of buildings for refurbishment and the intensity of renovation in percentage.

According to the selected scenario and the intensity level of the refurbishment, the user will be able to graphically compare the result of the intervention for the whole municipality or geographic area considered. It will also be possible to visualize the current state and rehabilitation scenarios in terms of primary energy use (Fig. 6) or EPC labels (Fig. 7).

Step 3 – The user obtains more detailed information about the retrofitting measures such as the return of investment and the maintenance costs, among others (Fig. 8). Information about the type of actions associated with the improvement options are detailed. Besides, the buildings to which the renovation measures can be applied are listed and displayed in the map.

Step 4 – Finally, the user downloads a report of the analysis in pdf format.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have developed an energy platform to create ad hoc services based on the integration of energy related data from multiple sources and domains. Two applications –for private building owners and public administrations– have been implemented to facilitate valuable information based on the integration of EPCs data with other data sources. From the implementation of these services the following conclusions can be derived:

- The qualified information that an energy information system such as ENERSI can facilitate is constrained by the

available data. For instance, final energy consumption and energy bills would be very relevant to assess the building energy performance of a building and to more precisely identify the measures to improve it, but EPC data only provides information about primary energy use.

- In addition, the reliability of the analysis of the integrated data depends on the reliability of the data sources. Since the reliability of EPC data is relatively low, mechanisms to validate these data are essential to perform credible energy analysis.

- The analysis of integrated data requires the development of ad hoc methods, specific for each particular problem case. There cannot be automatic procedures to create these methods.

- Despite ongoing efforts, standards are not fully harmonized. Very often there is more than one definition of a term.

- Energy information systems need to be maintained, to ensure that the information provided by the data sources is updated and consistent.

The two applications will be publicly available in the ENERSI web portal and in the websites of the public institutions which have provided their energy data to the project. Following the feedback received by expected users, the interfaces will be further developed and refined.

	Total	PE 1	PE 2	PE 3	PE 4	PE 5	PE 6	PE 7	PE 8	PE 9
Edificis amb lletra A	45 236	1 3	7 24	4 42	1 1	1 37	0 0	10 64	0 3	21 62
Edificis amb lletra B	128 3k	6 11	19 52	6 610	1 1	23 414	0 9	13 1k	3 14	57 351
Edificis amb lletra C	1k 18k	9 41	105 586	181 4k	2 10	137 3k	3 34	312 9k	9 69	399 1k
Edificis amb lletra D	9k 41k	62 219	960 3k	2k 9k	13 74	994 6k	18 77	3k 19k	52 109	1k 4k
Edificis amb lletra E	63k 32k	304 249	8k 8k	12k 9k	146 170	9k 4k	88 51	27k 11k	139 39	6k 4k
Edificis amb lletra F	8k 1k	71 34	1k 406	2k 152	49 22	1k 91	26 0	3k 25k	15 0	691 103
Edificis amb lletra G	15k 80k	110 16	2k 986	3k 245	64 8	2k 7k	37 1	8k 2k	16 0	930 104
Nº Edificis existents	96659	963	12384	19099	286	13549	172	40509	234	9847
Nº Edificis a rehabilitar	96659	963	12384	19099	286	13549	172	40509	234	9847
% Edificis a rehabilitar	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Mesures passives										
Estalvi d'energia i emissions (%)	41.03%	27.15%	26.25%	45.65%	19.25%	45.65%	40.75%	44.95%	34.20%	29.80%
Inversió per edifici	11796.07€	9407.80€	3433.30€	13788.00€	7124.60€	13788.00€	16002.00€	12030.90€	23669.80€	14656.20€
Inversió total (M€)	1140.20M€	5.30M€	42.52M€	263.28M€	2.04M€	187.09M€	2.75M€	487.36M€	5.54M€	144.32M€
Retorn de la inversió	32.61 Anys	26.65 Anys	20.70 Anys	33.20 Anys	32.05 Anys	33.20 Anys	33.95 Anys	29.00 Anys	39.60 Anys	45.10 Anys
Accions de millora		Mostrar								
Mesures actives										
Estalvi d'energia i emissions (%)	3.30%	3.78%	1.55%	2.48%	4.59%	3.60%	5.47%	3.62%	6.15%	4.46%
Inversió per edifici	768.44€	935.88€	374.40€	543.14€	1225.70€	733.21€	1330.23€	726.79€	1535.43€	934.95€

Fig. 7. Renew your city: Step 2 (EPC labels)

Pas 1		Pas 2		Pas 3		Pas 4		Pas 5	
Cerca un àmbit		Instruccions d'ús		Escenaris de rehabilitació		Menú d'intervenció		Informe final	
Filtra edificis									
Tots PE 1 PE 2 PE 3 PE 4 PE 5 PE 6 PE 7 PE 8 PE 9									
Vista resum Vista taula Vista mapa									
PE1 (Paquet d'edificis unifamiliars construïts abans del 1950 d'entre 1 i 3 plantes)	Edificis a aplicar	Inversió per edifici (€)	Estalvi energètic (%)	Retorn (Anys)					
Mesures passives									
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aplicar mur massís i gruixut en la façana. • Aplicar aïllament per a l'interior de la façana • Instal·lar marcs d'alumini amb RPT (ruptura de pont tèrmic) i vidre 4/12/4 en les obertures. • Instal·lar finestres PVC i vidre baix emissiu. • Instal·lar coberta inclinada amb càmera ventilada. • Aïllar la coberta per a l'interior • Solera en contacte amb el terreny. 	2011	9407€	23,4% - 30,9%	14,1 - 39,2					
Mesures actives									
A2. Caldera de condensació gasoil	1230	2600€	19,7% - 23,2%	5,2 - 12,9					
A3. Caldera de condensació gas natural	450	2600€	19,7% - 23,2%	3,5 - 8,6					
A4. Caldera de pellets	230	7650€	13,3% - 17,1%	41,8 - 10,4					

Fig. 8. Renew your city: Step 3

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been carried out within the research project ENERSI co-funded by the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness of the Government of Spain (Reference number RTC-2014-2676-3). We would like to thank the support of the Catalan Institute for Energy (ICAEN) for facilitating the EPCs data in Catalonia.

REFERENCES

- [1] U. Di Staso, L. Giovannini, M. Berti, F. Prandi, P. Cipriano, and R. De Amicis. "Large-Scale Residential Energy Maps: Estimation, Validation and Visualization Project SUNSHINE-Smart Urban Services for Higher Energy Efficiency," in International Conference on Data Management Technologies and Applications, Springer International Publishing, pp. 28-44, 2014.
- [2] Institut Català de l'Energia. Simulador de medidas de rehabilitación energética de edificios <http://simuladoredificis.icaen.gencat.cat/>
- [3] ISO. (2008). ISO 13790: 2008 (E). Energy performance of buildings - Calculation of energy use for space heating and cooling. International Organization for Standardization.
- [4] T. Loga, N. Diefenbach, Eds. DATAMINE. Collecting Data from Energy Certification to Monitor Performance Indicators for New and Existing buildings. Final report. Darmstadt, Germany: Institut Wohnen und Umwelt GmbH, 2009.
- [5] Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings.
- [6] Orden FOM/1635/2013, de 10 de septiembre, por la que se actualiza el Documento Básico DB-HE "Ahorro de Energía", del Código Técnico de la Edificación, aprobado por Real Decreto 314/2006, de 17 de marzo.
- [7] Ministerio de Fomento. (2014). Estrategia a largo plazo para la rehabilitación energética en el sector de la edificación en España en desarrollo del artículo 4 de la Directiva 2012/27/UE. Madrid: Ministerio de Fomento.